

THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT AND FORMATION OF JAPANESE JOURNALISM

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ANNOTATION

In the modern world the role of Japan in international political processes is increasing and makes it more and more important to understand cultural codes, including the characteristics of the Japanese media. The level of journalism in the Land of the Rising Sun is comparable with that of the developed countries of the world, but it has its own features based on the traditions and characteristics of Japanese national culture. The Japanese media market is one of the richest and most developed in the world.

Key words: *journalism, print media, Japan, national culture, media. Japanese journalism is one of the most formalized in the world. The media presents events directly related to Japan, but the interesting fact is that events occurring in the world are covered sparingly in the Japanese press. Japan is also considered one of the most reading countries. According to the survey conducted by the Japan Newspaper Publishers Association, the average amount of time people spend on reading newspapers is 44.1 minutes per day, 24.8 minutes to read books, and 16.8 minutes to read magazines, while only 3.6% of those surveyed do not read newspapers [1].*

Thus, in this article we will consider "journalism" as a type of creative human activity. Journalism reflects and shapes public consciousness, serves society and at the

same time is a means of social management. Speaking of journalism in Japan, it can be divided into five main layers:

- News journalism-includes federal (important events in Japan) and regional (or "prefectural") journalism, the social life of Japan.

- Cooking and restaurant journalism.

- Journalism of various specialties.

- Journalism about adult culture, manga and anime, and others.

Japanese people are highly dependent on public opinion. And when journalistic materials published in the media contain negative evaluations and criticism, they can deeply depress the hero of the publication, up to and including suicide attempts. That is why the only basic principles of Japanese journalism are verified information and honesty. Reputation is of paramount importance [2].

There is virtually no "made-to-order" journalism in Japan; it is impossible to buy articles that are known to be erroneous or untrue. In 1938, the Japanese newspaper Yomiuri Shimbun set up a committee to control the quality of journalism, which evolved into the Press Ombudsman Commission in 1951. It still hears complaints about the newspaper from readers and meets with editors every day. The press ombudsman is a member of the media who receives and investigates complaints from readers, viewers, and listeners and resolves conflicts between readers and the media [3].

Advertising is actively used in Japanese journalism. Many Japanese media, especially print media, are a kind of "information department store" in terms of content, providing materials for all categories of readers and actively using advertising texts and various types of advertising messages [1].

Newspapers play an important role in Japanese life because newspapers have a number of advantages over television, radio, and magazines. Moreover, 64.3% of Japanese people consider newspapers the most reliable media, 67.9% say they are accurate and trustworthy, 50.6% say they help businesses (this is especially true for the

Nikkei and Yomiuri), and finally, 48.8% say that, like television, newspapers shape their views and opinions of society [4].

The origins of print journalism in Japan go back to the Middle Ages, when so-called "illustrative journalism" began to appear [5]. At the beginning of their development in Japan, newspapers were divided into two categories: "big newspapers," which published political articles and foreign news, and "small newspapers," which were entertainment publications. The beginning of general newspapers was marked by the appearance of the first daily newspaper, the Yokohama Mainichi Shimbun [5]. This newspaper was the first newspaper in Japan to deal with human rights issues. It was also the first newspaper to cover local and foreign news simultaneously: the Tokyo Nichinichi Shimbun was launched in 1872 and the Osaka Mainichi Shimbun in 1876. After 1943, the two newspapers merged to form the Mainichi Shimbun, which today is one of the largest periodicals in Japan. In 1887, after strict publishing and censorship rules were abolished, the newspaper business took off, contributing to such famous newspapers as: "Yomiuri Shimbun," "Osaka Asahi Shimbun," and "Tokyo Asahi Shimbun." [4]

In 1890, the Kokumin Shimbun began to be published, with Tokufu Soho as the editor of the newspaper and his newspaper articles becoming regarded as the "voice of the nation." [6]

The late 19th century was also the beginning of the emergence of English-language newspapers in Japan. The Japan Times was founded in 1897 with the aim of involving Japan in international affairs and covering local news abroad [5].

The year 1924 marked the introduction of publication control, this contributed to the emergence of a special police force as well as a change in laws. One important law in pre-war Japan was the Prevention of Dangerous Ideas Law ("Tenichi Law") passed in 1925. In the postwar period, to protect political independence, represent the interests of the newspaper industry, and prevent deviations from journalistic ethics and standards, the representatives of publications established the Japan Newspaper Publishers and Editors (Jap) Association.

"Japan Newspaper Publishers and Editors," which in 1972 had 166 members, including major newspaper groups [7]. Membership in the association requires strict adherence to rules and norms. This led to the formation of a code of journalistic practice, which includes the following provisions: freedom of the press, the principle of editorial commentary, impartiality, tolerance, leadership, responsibility and honesty [7]. Thus, newspaper reports remain popular in modern Japanese society, although their role has significantly decreased with the advent of television and the Internet. Despite the formality of modern Japanese journalism, which follows the accepted standards and traditions of Japan, it reveals the unique appeal of the Land of the Rising Sun.

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